

contained 7.3% P, of which 20.3% was citric acid soluble. The pyrite contained 9.2% sulfur and 11.6% iron. Application was based on total P of the rock phosphate. Three equal splits of 100 kg N/ha were applied at planting, tillering, and panicle initiation and 50 kg K/ha was

applied as muriate of potash at planting.

Soil samples were collected after three seasons and analyzed to determine residual effects of the treatment (see table). Data indicated that the rock phosphate-pyrite mixture could be a good substitute for single superphosphate in

neutral and high pH soils. The rock phosphate treatment exhibited better residual response under neutral soil conditions, as reflected by a 14.6% yield increase (see table). It cost 1/3 less per hectare to apply rock phosphate than to apply a single superphosphate. □

Effect of straw management on soil nitrogen in a rice — wheat rotation

N. S. Dhillon and G. Dev, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, India

Farmers are using more combine-type harvesting machines and therefore are burning more rice and wheat straw in Punjab. Burning crop residues in the field may change soil nutrients, especially the C, N, P, S ratio, and other physico-chemical and biological soil properties. The effect of straw management on soil N in a rice - wheat rotation was studied in a farmer's field in Kasabad, Ludhiana. Soil was sandy loam with pH 8.3 and E.C. 0.45 mmho/cm.

After wheat was combine-harvested in May 1980, the field was divided into three plots for straw removal, incorporation, and burning. Each plot was divided into 24 plots for 3 replications of 8 fertilizer treatments — 0, 50, 100, and 150 kg N/ha as urea with and without 22 kg P/ha as single superphosphate. The experiment was repeated after the 1980 rice harvest, the 1980-81 wheat harvest, and the 1981 rice harvest. Soil was sampled (0-15 cm depth) after harvest and analyzed for available N, total N, organic N, and organic carbon.

Fertilizer treatments did not significantly affect soil N. Therefore the data for the straw management practices were pooled (see table).

Straw incorporation significantly in-

creased organic carbon, total N, hexosamine N, and amino acid N. Burning or removing the straw after each crop harvest increased nonhydrolyzable N in the soil. Burning straw lowered total N by 11%, hydrolyzable N 31%, hexosamine N 88%, and amino acid N 60%. $\text{KMnO}_4\text{-N}$ and hydrolyzable $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$, hexosamine N, and amino acid N levels were significantly higher where straw was incorporated.

Available N level was low, and decreased with cropping. Where straw was continuously incorporated, total N increased by about 20% after 4 crops. It decreased by about 10% where straw was burned. Amino acid N increased in straw-incorporation plots. Hexosamine N and amino acid N decreased after rice but increased after wheat. □

Organic carbon and soil nitrogen as affected by various straw management practices, Punjab, India.

Soil N form	Initial level	1980 after rice			1980-81 after wheat			1981 after rice			1981-82 after wheat			CD (5.0%)
		Straw incorporation	Straw removal	Straw burning	Straw incorporation	Straw removal	Straw burning	Straw incorporation	Straw removal	Straw burning	Straw incorporation	Straw removal	Straw burning	
Organic carbon (%)	0.54	0.52	0.52	0.48	0.55	0.55	0.54	0.61	0.57	0.54	0.62	0.56	0.53	0.02
$\text{KMnO}_4\text{-N}$ ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	84	55	53	64	50	48	46	58	48	46	55	50	46	5.3
Total N ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	486	503	486	455	516	481	464	569	498	450	582	486	435	17.4
Hydrolyzable-N ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	311	298	301	219	311	276	219	332	280	214	336	289	214	13.5
Nonhydrolyzable-N ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	195	204	183	234	205	205	249	236	218	236	246	267	221	28.4
Hydrolyzable $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	112	124	105	106	121	107	107	117	105	115	105	98	103	6.4
Hexosamine-N ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	42	33	20	16	53	23	9	47	19	4	55	22	5	4.5
Amino acid-N ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	112	121	109	39	138	117	44	145	131	51	152	133	45	5.6

Performance of modified urea fertilizer on a sandy loam soil

O. P. Meelu and R. S. Rekhi, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University (PAU), Ludhiana, India

Urea is the commonly used nitrogen fertilizer in India. Nitrogen losses through ammonia volatilization are often high. Use of controlled-release N fertilizers and

urea supergranules has been advocated to increase N-use efficiency in rice.

The efficiency of modified urea materials was compared to that of split applications of prilled urea at the PAU farm in Ludhiana. Soil was a Fatehpur sandy loam (Typic Ustipsamment) with pH 8.4, 0.35% organic carbon. 62 kg available N/ha with a percolation rate of 7 mm/h, and CEC 5.3 meq/100 g soil. Prilled urea, sulfur-coated urea (SCU),

urea supergranules (USG), lac-coated urea (LCU), and neem-cake-treated urea (NCU) were tested. All modified urea materials were applied in a single dose at transplanting. Prilled urea was applied either all at transplanting or in 3 equal splits: at transplanting, 21, and 42 days after transplanting. USG was point-placed 10 cm deep between 4 plants in alternate rows. All urea was applied at 120 kg N/ha. A basal dose of 13 kg P and 25 kg